

FISH BRANHIOMYCOSIS PREVENTION MEASURES.**G.I.Abdusalilova**Student of Samarkand State University of
Veterinary Medicine, Animal Husbandry
and Biotechnology, Tashkent branch**M.U.Makhamadaliyeva**Student of Samarkand State University of
Veterinary Medicine, Animal Husbandry
and Biotechnology, Tashkent branch**Sh.I.Khojakhanov**Independent researcher of Samarkand State
University of Veterinary Medicine, Animal
Husbandry and Biotechnology, Tashkent branch
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7809783>

Annotation: Branchymycosis - decay of wounds. Acute infectious disease is characterized by injury of the blood vessels of the wound apparatus and necrosis of the tissue of the wound sheets.

Аннотация: Бранхимикоз – загнивание ран. Острое инфекционное заболевание характеризуется поражением сосудов раневого аппарата и некрозом тканей раневых листов.

Annotatsiya: Branximikoz -jabralarning chirishi. O'tkir kontagioz kassallik, jabra apparatining qon tomirlari jarohatlanishi va jabra varaqlari to'qimasining nekrozga uchrashi bilan karakterlanadi.

Key words: Branchiomyces, leukogram, Bronchiomyces sanguinis, Bronchiomyces sanguinis, epizotia, enzotia.

Ключевые слова: бранхимикоз, лейкограмма, Bronchiomyces sanguinis, Bronchiomyces sanguinis, эпизотия, энзотия.

Kalit so'zlar: Branximikoz, leykogramma, Bronchiomyces sanguinis, Bronchiomyces sanguinis, epizotiya, enzotiya.

Introduction: Among the vertebrates, fishes are of special importance, and today 84 species of fishes are recorded in the reservoirs of our republic. Carps are widespread in the water bodies of Uzbekistan and consist of more than 45 species and subspecies (Mirabdullayev et al., 2001; Shernazarov et al., 2006). Fish products are important in meeting the population's demand for protein and vitamins. That is why the government of the republic has been paying great attention to the development of fisheries in recent years. In particular, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 350 dated August 13, 2003 "On measures to remove monopoly and deepen privatization in the fishing industry", adopted by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan on August 26, 2009 On the basis of the "Program on Measures for the Development of the Fisheries Network in the Republic" adopted in February, fisheries development programs were developed in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, regions and all districts. However, there are many factors that seriously hinder the development of the industry. One of such factors in the development of fisheries is fish diseases, which have a negative impact on the development of the sector. The development of fisheries diseases and their prevention measures is of great importance today.

Relevance of the topic: Fish diseases caused by fungi are characterized by the fact that they cause mass death among all fish diseases. It poses a great danger, especially in the conditions of intensification of the fishing network. Despite the fact that these diseases originated in fishing farms a long time ago, they have not been well studied until now. An absolutely accurate method of diagnosis has not been developed, the epizootology and pathogenesis of the disease have not been well studied, and effective methods of measures to prevent and combat the disease have not been developed. [1]

Causes of the disease: The causative agent of the disease is 2 types of parasitic fungi. One of them - *Branchiomyces sanguinis* - infects crucian carp, small crucian carp, heeler, and stone carp. The second type, *Branchiomyces demigrans*, infects cod. Both species parasitize linfish. *Branchiomyces sanguinis* is a special blood parasite. The hyphae of the fungus are unobstructed, highly elongated, 8 μm thick, and are found only in the blood vessels of the gill arches, sheets, and respiratory folds. The mycelium of *Branchiomyces demigrans* is composed of woody branching hyphae. The hyphae are up to 30 μm wide and 0.5 to 0.7 μm thick. As the fungus parasitises the veins, it also parasitises the connective tissue of the wound.[2,5]

Clinical signs: The disease is acute and lasts from 5 to 12 days. Sick fish do not feed, lose weight, the response to external influences is weakened, accumulate on the surface of the water, swim vertically, but do not breathe air. As a result of observations, we can see uneven "marble" coloring of jabra leaves, turning into gray, reddish, brown and blue colors. Some parts die and turn dark gray. Injuries remain as if eaten.[7]

The condition of the wound in branchiomycosis.

The mortality rate of one-year and two-year-old fish rises to 70%. In surviving fish, the disease turns into a slightly acute and chronic period. Recovery of injuries can be extended for 1 year or more. At the beginning of the disease, when the fungus *Branchiomyces Sanqiuinis* enters the blood vessels of the affected areas, there are cases of spot bleeding, then hyphae of

the fungus grow inside the affected blood vessel, causing its filling (parasitic embolism) and blood circulation disorders. , as a result, the blood supply to some parts of the injured tissue deteriorates, it becomes pale. Some parts die and the corners of the wound become uneven. Other parts of the wound become bluish due to the accumulation of blood in the blood vessels. Diseased fish do not take food, the response to external stimuli is sharply reduced or does not respond at all, floats to the surface of the water, but does not take in air, like a "zamor" and it becomes much easier to catch fish by hand. Heavily infected fish lie on their side and die in this position. The death rate reaches 50-70%, and in the fish that did not die, the disease passes in a semi-acute or chronic form. It seems that the fish that have recovered from the disease have been eaten. It takes years to recover.[6,4]

Disease treatment and prevention measures: For the treatment of infected fish, 0.05 g/kg mini feed of fungicide antibiotic grisin is given continuously for 3 days. As soon as the first symptoms are noticed, quarantine is announced on the farm, water flow is accelerated, oxygen is enriched with aerators, water is purified using quicklime at 150 kg/ha, this work is carried out from May until the pH rises to 8.0. Fish dead from branchiomycosis are cleaned. The dead are buried. Healthy fish are sold, and poor quality fish are boiled as feed for birds and animals.[3]

Conclusion: The difference between branchiomycosis and zamor disease is that fish do not lift their heads out of the water to breathe. As soon as the first symptoms are noticed, quarantine is announced on the farm, water flow is accelerated, oxygen is enriched with aerators, water is treated with 150 kg/ha of quicklime, this work is done from May until the pH rises to 8.0. activities are important factors in disease treatment and prevention.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar Qo'shimcha adabiyotlar:

1. Герасимчик В.А. Садовникова Е.Ф. "Болезни рыб и пчел", учебное пособие Минск 2017.
2. Головина Н.А. и другие "Ихтиопатология", учебник, Издательство "Мир" 2003.
3. Грищенко Л.И. и другие "Болезни рыб и основы рыбоводства" учебник, Москва "Колос" 1999.
4. Kamilov B.G., Xalilova I.I. "O'zbekiston sharoitida daryo forelini yetishtirish", fermerlarn uchun tavsiyalar. Toshkent-2014.
5. Haqberdiyev P.S., Davlatov R.B. "Baliqlarni saqlash, oziqlantirish, ularning kasalliklarini davolash va oldini olish", o'quv qo'llanma. Samarqand-2012.
6. Eshburiyev, S. B., Kasimov, S. J., & Aslonova, M. A. (2023). Causes and symptoms of protein metabolism disorders in fish. In Proceedings of International Conference on Scientific Research in Natural and Social Sciences (Vol. 2, No. 1, pp. 55-63).
7. Daminov, A. S., Nasimov, S. N., Gerasimchik, V. A., Eshburiyev, S. B., & Qurbonov, F. I. (2022). Baliq kasalliklari.
1. ДАВЛАТОВ, Р. Б., & ИБРАГИМОВ, Д. (2012). Сравнительная активность кокцидиостатиков при эймериозе птиц. Вестник ветеринарии, (4), 40-41.
2. Давлатов, Р. Б., & Хушназаров, А. Х. (2022). ҚУЁН ЭЙМЕРИОЗИ ЭПИЗООТОЛОГИЯСИ ДАВОЛАШ ВА ПРОФИЛАКТИКА ЧОРА-ТАДБИРЛАРИ. АГРОБИОТЕХНОЛОГИЯ ВА ВЕТЕРИНАРИЯ ТИВВИЙОТИ ИLMИЙ JURNALI, 181-184.
3. Давлатов, Р. Б., Салимов, Х. С., & Худжамшукуров, А. Н. (2018). Парранда касалликлари" ўқув қўлланма Самарқанд.

4. Давлатов, Р., & Мишин, В. (2008). Одновременная профилактика эймериоза и колибактериоза. Животноводство России, (5), 17-18.
5. Давлатов, Р. Б., Насимов, Ш. Н., Ниёзов, Х. Б., Жабборов, Ш. А., Хўджамшукуров, Ш. А., & Сафаров, Х. А. (2019). Парранда касалликларини профилактикаси ва даволаш бўйича ТАВСИЯЛАР. Тошкент-2019, 21-26.
6. Давлатов, Р. Б., Расулов, У. И., & Исломов, Г. П. (2018). МЕТОДЫ ТЕРАПИИ И ПРОФИЛАКТИКИ ПИРОПЛАЗМОЗА КРУПНОГО РОГАТОГО СКОТА. In Современное состояние, традиции и инновационные технологии в развитии АПК (pp. 73-76).
7. Давлатов, Р. (2008). Коликокцид-препарат против эймериоза и колибактериоза птицы. Птицеводство, (1), 28-28.
8. Gafurov, A. G., Davlatov, R. B., & Rasulov, U. I. (2011). Protozoal diseases of farm animals.
9. Ниязов, Ф. А., Давлатов, Р. Б., & Дурдиев, Ш. К. (2007). Особенности ассоциированного течения эймериоза и колибактериоза птиц. In Болезни птиц в промышленном птицеводстве. Современное состояние проблемы и стратегия борьбы. Матер. научно-произв. конф (pp. 324-327).
10. Рустамов, Б. С., & Давлатов, Р. Б. (2019). СПЕЦИФИЧЕСКАЯ АКТИВНОСТЬ ПРЕПАРАТОВ ПРИ ГИСТОМОНОЗЕ ИНДЕЕК. In СОВРЕМЕННОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ, ТРАДИЦИИ И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В РАЗВИТИИ АПК (pp. 116-119).
11. Гафуров, А. Г., Давлатов, Р. Б., & Расулов, У. И. (2013). Ветеринарная протозоология. Учебник для ВУЗа.-Т.:«Зарафшан.
12. Хушназаров, А. Х., Райимкулов, И. Х., Эшқораев, А. М., & Давлатов, Р. Б. (2023). ҚУЁН ЭЙМЕРИОЗИНИНГ КИМЁПРОФИЛАКТИКАСИ. SCHOLAR, 1(2), 56-62.
13. Давлатов, Р. Б., & Бердиев, Х. Р. (2021). ТОВУҚ КОЛИБАКТЕРИОЗИНИНГ КИМЁПРОФИЛАКТИКАСИДА ОФЛОСАННИНГ САМАРАДОРЛИГИ. Вестник Ветеринарии и Животноводства, 1(1).
14. Бердиев, Х. Р., & Давлатов, Р. Б. (2021). Эффективность Enrovit-0 при химической профилактике колибактериоза цыплят.
15. Худжамшукуров, А. Н., & Давлатов, Р. Б. (2019). РАСПРОСТРАНЕНИЕ ЭЙМЕРИОЗА КУР В УСЛОВИЯХ УЗБЕКИСТАНА И ИСПЫТАНИЕ ЭЙМЕРИОСТАТИКОВ ДЛЯ ЕГО ПРОФИЛАКТИКИ. In СОВРЕМЕННОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ, ТРАДИЦИИ И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ В РАЗВИТИИ АПК (pp. 167-171).
16. Berdiyevich, D. R. (2023). TO DETERMINE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ANTIBIOTICS IN PREVENTING CHICKEN COLIBACTERIOSIS BASED ON EXPERIMENTS.
17. Рустамов, Б. С., & Давлатов, Р. Б. (2021). КУРКАЛАР ГИСТОМОНОЗИНИ ДАВОЛАШ ВА ОЛДИНИ ОЛИШДА ВИТАМИНЛИ КОМПЛЕКСЛАРНИ СИНОВДАН ЎТКАЗИШ. ВЕСТНИК ВЕТЕРИНАРИИ И ЖИВОТНОВОДСТВА, 1(2).
18. Butaeva, I. M., Salimov, H. S., & Davlatov, R. B. (2020). On The Diagnosis Of Mixed Bacterial Infections Of Birds. International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology, 29(9s), 2308-2315.
19. Давлатов, Р. Б., Салимов, Х. С., & Тоиров, Ж. Э. (2018). ВОПРОСЫ ЭПИЗОТОЛОГИИ ЭШЕРИХИОЗА ПТИЦ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. In Современное состояние, традиции и инновационные технологии в развитии АПК (pp. 67-73).
20. Давлатов, Р. Б. (1993). Совершенствование методов борьбы с аскариозом кур.

21. Rustamov, B. S., & Davlatov, R. B. Prevalence and Treatment of Turkeys Histomonosissamarkand Institute of Veterinary Medicine. International Journal of Innovations in Engineering Research and Technology, (1), 1-5.
22. Давлатов, Р. Б. (2023). ТОВУҚ КОЛИБАКТЕРИОЗИ (АДАБИЁТЛАР ШАРХИ). INNOVATION IN THE MODERN EDUCATION SYSTEM, 3(26), 107-111.
23. Oripov, A. O., Davlatov, R. B., & Yo'ldoshiv, N. E. (2016). Veterinariya gelmintologiyasi. Toshkent-2016.
24. Давлатов, Р. Б., Салимов, Х. С., & Хўджамшукуров, А. Н. Паррандалар касалликлари. Ўқув қўлланма, Самарқанд-2018.
25. Давлатов, Р. Б., Салимов, Х. С., & Тоиров, Ж. Э. ЧУВСТВИТЕЛЬНОСТЬ КОЛИБАКТЕРИОЗА ПТИЦ К АНТИБИОТИКАМ КОЛИБАКТЕРИОЗИС SENSITIVITY TO ANTIBIOTICS. ББК 65.2 С56, 39.
26. Oripov, A. O., Davlatov, R. B., & Yuldashiv, N. E. Veterinary helminthology. Tashkent-2016.
27. Oglu, K. S. I., & Qizi, K. B. A. (2022). MEASURES FOR THE PREVENTION OF DISEASES CAUSED BY DISORDERS OF BEE NUTRITION AND FEEDING CONDITIONS. Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research, 3(3), 1-4.
28. Zayniddinovich, Z. R. (2022). REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE ON SEPSIS IN CALVES AND MEASURES TO PREVENT IT. Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning, 3(1), 1-4.
29. Zayniddinovich, Z. R. (2022). REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE ON SEPSIS IN CALVES AND MEASURES TO PREVENT IT. Emergent: Journal of Educational Discoveries and Lifelong Learning, 3(1), 1-4.
30. Oglu, K. S. I., Oglu, Y. O. A., & Oglu, J. S. H. (2021). Viral hemorrhagic fever of rabbits ("hemorrhagic pneumonia", "necrotic hepatitis").
31. Subxonovich, H. P., Ergashevna, G. M., & Ogli, K. S. I. (2021). Distribution of helminthosis diseases of one-hoied animals. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(10), 880-883.
32. Mahamadaliyeva, M. U., & Agamurodov, O. A. (2021). MEASURES FOR TREATMENT AND PREVENTION OF DISPEPS DISEASE IN CALVES. Ученый XXI века, (10 (81)), 12-14.
33. Nurmatovich, K. A., & Ogli, K. S. I. (2021). Effects of drugs on blood indicators in mixing chicken eimeriosis and pullorosis. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal, 11(5), 615-617.
34. Davlatov, R., Xujaxonov, S., & Berdiyev, X. (2021). ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ОФЛОСАНА В ХИМИЧЕСКОЙ ПРОФИЛАКТИКЕ КОЛИБАКТЕРИОЗА КУРИЦ. Вестник ветеринарии и животноводства (ssuv.uz), 1(1).
35. БУЗИЛИШЛАРИ, Ё. Улуқов Беҳзод Каромат ўғли магистранти, Хўжахонов Шохрузхон Идиришўжа ўғли магистранти, Жуманазарова Мадина Қахрамон қизи.
36. Хушназаров, А., & Давлатов, Р. (2023). Қуён эймериозининг тарқалиши ва патологоанатомик ташҳиси. in Library, 1(1), 15-17.
37. Хушназаров, А., & Давлатов, Р. Б. (2022). Quyon eumeriozini davolashda vazuril preparatining samaradorligi. in Library, 22(2), 173-174.
38. Khushnazarov, A. K., & Davlatov, R. B. (2023). DIAGNOSTICS OF RABBIT EMERIOSIS. Journal of new century innovations, 22(3), 72-77.

39. Khushnazarov, A. K., Eshkorayev, A. M., & Davlatov, R. B. (2023). DEVELOPMENT, EPISOTOLGY, TREATMENT AND PREVENTIVE MEASURES OF EMERIOSIS IN RABBITS. Journal of new century innovations, 22(3), 65-71.
40. Ergashov, S. I., Xushnazarov, A. X., & Davlatov, R. B. (2023). QUYONLAR EYMERIOZNI DAVOLASHDA KENG QO 'LLANILADIGAN PREPARATLAR. Journal of new century innovations, 22(3), 58-64.
41. Хушназаров, А., Хабибулаев, С. Л., Рахматова, У., Орлова, Г. И., Толибова, Ф. Т., & Хушназарова, М. И. (2022). Quyunchilik xo'jaliklarini eymeriozdan asrash. in Library, 22(2), 5-8.
42. Махамдалиева, М. У., Абдухалилова, Г. И., & Хо'jaxonov, S. I. (2023). BRUTSELLYOZ VA UNING LABORATORIYA DIAGNOSTIKASI. INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION, 2(15), 41-47.
43. G'oyipova, M. T. E., Xo'jaxonov, S., & Avliyoqulov, M. (2022). VETERINARIYA SOHASINING CHORVACHILIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDAGI O 'RNI VA TAMOYILLARI. Journal of Integrated Education and Research, 1(4), 238-240.
44. БУЗИЛИШЛАРИ, Ё. Улуқов Беҳзод Каромат ўғли магистранти, Хўжахонов Шохрузхон Идирисхўжа ўғли магистранти, Жуманазарова Мадина Қаҳрамон қизи.
45. Oglu, K. S. I., Zayniddinovich, Z. R., & Oglu, R. J. K. (2022). Review of the literature on sepsis in calves and measures to prevent it.
46. Худжамшукуров, А. Н. (2021). ТОВУҚ АСКАРИДИОЗИДА АСКАЗИН АНТИГЕЛЬМИНТИГИНИ ҚЎЛЛАШ НАТИЖАЛАРИ. Интернаука, (8-3), 44-46.

